

**UNDERLYING FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO ALCOHOL ABUSE AMONG
STUDENTS IN KITWE'S COPPERBELT REGION.**

By

Preston Mwiinga

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ABBREVIATIONS/ ACRONYMS:

DEC	Drug Enforcement Commission
NIAAA	National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism
NIDA	National Institute of Drug Abuse
UNODC	United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime
WHO	World Health Organisation

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to uncover the multifaceted factors contributing to alcohol abuse among students specifically at the Riverside Campus of COPPERBELT University in KITWE district. Delving into social, economic, and service-related realms, the research explored the intricate influences fueling alcohol misuse among university students. Employing a cross-sectional approach, both qualitative and quantitative methodologies were integrated to yield comprehensive insights. While quantitative analysis provided numerical data scrutiny, the qualitative method facilitated a deeper understanding through participant questionnaires.

The findings of the study underscored the significant impact of social, economic, and service-related factors on alcohol misuse within the university setting. It emphasizes the need for establishing a supportive educational environment that encourages active engagement in extracurricular activities, such as sports and music, as potential preventive measures against alcohol abuse among students

CHAPTER 1
INTRODUCTION
1.1 BACKGROUND

Alcohol consumption globally presents a critical concern, notably with the increasing involvement of school-age children. In 2016, hazardous alcohol use, as reported by the World Health Organization (2018), led to over 3 million deaths, impacting a staggering 2.3 billion drinkers worldwide. The widespread abuse of drugs and alcohol is a pervasive global issue, directly impeding the freedom and development of the world's youth, as highlighted by UNODC (2015). The severity and characteristics of this problem vary across countries and regions, yet the escalation of youth drug and alcohol misuse has reached unprecedented levels. The World Drug Report (Lakhampal and Agnihotri, 2012) indicates that of the 180 million drug users worldwide, a substantial portion comprises young individuals, with alcohol, tobacco, and marijuana ranking as the most commonly abused substances among adolescents on a global scale (Bourne, 2016).

Presently, WHO (2018) estimates that there are approximately 2.3 billion drinkers, and the misuse of drugs among young people is a pervasive issue affecting virtually all nations. Research indicates that many adolescents experiment with alcohol or drugs before entering school, although quantifying the precise extent and nature of student drug consumption can pose challenges. Notably, approximately 10% of female adolescents and 25% of male adolescents engage in weekly alcohol abuse. As highlighted in the UNDCP assessment (2013), alcohol abuse profoundly impacts families and communities across continents, notably in Africa. While alcohol misuse spans various age groups, its prevalence peaks during adolescence and early adulthood, fostering risky behaviors such as unsafe sex, smoking, and other perilous activities. Adolescents, driven by concepts of impression-making and rewards,

are particularly prone to risk-taking behaviors during this transitional phase into adulthood. Alcohol usage in Africa has been linked to mental health issues, unsafe sexual practices, and traffic accidents (Swahm et al., 2017).

Several demographic factors influence alcohol use, including gender, age, income, living circumstances, attitudes towards alcohol, perceived susceptibility, self-efficacy, peer influence, accessibility, exposure to anti-alcohol campaigns or advertising, and ownership of alcohol promotional materials (Swahm et al., 2017). The nuanced impact of alcohol consumption varies among individuals based on these distinct factors, yet it remains an influential force shaping behaviors and outcomes, especially among young people

In a comprehensive four-year study conducted in Brazil by Tavares et al. (2013), it was found that vulnerability to substance use among teenagers was notably high, and once this behavior is adopted during adolescence, it often becomes deeply ingrained as they mature. It's critical to educate youth about the perils of drug and alcohol addiction to prevent them from falling into a potentially lifelong trap, as Sulliman (2015) observed that despite efforts to prevent drug initiation among the 18-24 age bracket, many youth, particularly those in and out of school, still engage in substance use.

The situation in Africa mirrors this concern. Nielsen (2019) highlighted that 56% of the African population comprises secondary school pupils, aged 14 to 19, a susceptible age group to drug use. For instance, in Ethiopia's capital, Addis Ababa, a concerning 82% of street youth exhibit a tendency to use narcotics. Additionally, South Africa's role as a significant trans-shipment hub and dagaa producer contributes to the demand for drugs across the continent. This underscores the urgent need to combat drug usage.

Alcohol use disorders, including dependence and harmful consumption, significantly impact Zambia, as reported in the WHO World Health Report 2014. In Zambia, 7.9% of males and 1.0% of females experienced alcohol use disorders over a year, contributing to an overall rate

of 4.5%, surpassing the WHO African Region's average of 3.3% (World Health Organization, Zambia, 2019). Moreover, research indicates high alcohol consumption rates among Zambians, with 26.3% prevalence in urban Lusaka in 2011 (43.5% among men and 17.7% among women). Shockingly, one in three Zambian teenagers have been reported to consume alcohol (Muula et al., 2017).

The World Health Organization (WHO) has prioritized reducing global alcohol-related harm, focusing on technical support and monitoring to address this public health challenge. Research plays a vital role in guiding informed alcohol policies and decision-making (World Health Organization, 2019).

To effectively mitigate alcohol misuse among high school students, rapid and effective intervention strategies for both boys and girls are imperative. Educating parents about the risks associated with alcohol consumption among high school students is crucial in preventing risky behaviors. Without parental awareness, preventing the rise of alcohol consumption among high schoolers becomes increasingly challenging, as evident in Zambia (Nzala et al., 2011). Implementing preventative and control measures is crucial to curb this trend.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

WHO in 2019 reported that alcohol consumption is a factor in 60 different disease types and a component cause of 200 more diseases worldwide, affecting drinkers of all ages. This indicates that drinking alcohol is a significant worldwide etiological factor in many diseases. Despite these details, among young people and other groups, the use of alcohol and other drugs has continuing in many areas, and the circumstance appears to have reached previously unheard-of heights (WHO, 2019).

Alcohol drinking has a long history in Zambian society which is one of the countries in Africa where alcohol abuse is most common. Alcohol abuse is a serious issue in Zambia. 76 percent

of males and 33 percent of women in Zambia are said to consume too much, according to a World Health Organization research. It is concerning how widespread alcohol misuse is in Zambia's higher education facilities. A study at the University of Zambia indicated that, on average, 35% of female students and 33% of male students had consumed alcohol on occasion within previous 12 months (Swahn, 2011).

Statistics by the Drug Enforcement Commission (2022) showed about 43.4% of students in Kitwe abused alcohol in 2021. The extent of alcohol abuse in tertiary institutions in Zambia is alarming. According to the data that are currently accessible, alcohol usage starts before students enrol in academic institutions. According to national statistics, more than 74% of secondary school pupils start drinking before they turn 18 years old. As per data shown in earlier parts, rapes, traffic accidents, and illnesses linked to alcohol misuse are all frequent among young people. Several research link unhealthy alcohol consumption to the high HIV incidence among students in institutions (Ham, 2013).

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

The Drug Enforcement Commission (2022) reports a concerning 43.4% alcohol abuse rate among Kitwe's student population. Despite this statistic, there's a dearth of information detailing the factors that drive alcohol abuse among students in the Kitwe district. Therefore, the findings from this research will not only contribute significantly to understanding the factors that lead to alcohol abuse among students but will also provide crucial insights for institution management and policymakers. This insight will aid in formulating more effective programs to combat and prevent further alcohol abuse.

This study aims to pinpoint the specific risk factors influencing alcohol abuse among students at Copperbelt University. By identifying these risk factors, the study seeks to establish protective measures for both the current and future generations, contributing to more informed and targeted interventions in addressing alcohol abuse within the university setting.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

1.4.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To determine the factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at the Copperbelt University.

1.4.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To determine the social factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University.
2. To determine economic factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University.
3. To determine service related factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the Social factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University?
2. What are the economic factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University?
3. What are the service related factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University?

1.6 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Factors leading to the abuse of alcohol among students at The Copperbelt University.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables.

CHAPTER 2
LITERATURE REVIEW
2.0 INTRODUCTION

An overview of the literature on alcohol abuse among college students will be presented in this chapter. The review of the literature will generally concentrate on studies that have examined the underlying factors of alcohol abuse among university student's prevalence rates, and effects, as well as global, African, and Zambian mitigation strategies.

2.1 PREVALENCE OF ALCOHOL ABUSE

About two billion individuals have drunk alcoholic beverages at that time, according to the WHO's 2004 global status report on alcohol. According to Plant and Plant (1999), the social agenda of many nations had included the use of illicit alcohol for a long time. Over the past 30 years, illicit alcohol use among adults and young people has steadily increased in the UK and elsewhere. Young people in their early and mid-teens were consuming alcohol as a recreational substance and as a part of their free time, according to Miller and Plant's (2011) explanation. Between 12 and 14 million adults in the United States of America, according to Web Med, engaged in alcohol abuse or were chronic alcoholics. Each year, alcohol-related illnesses claim the lives of close to 100,000 Americans, and more than half of all homicides, suicides, and traffic fatalities in the nation involved alcohol. Alcoholism contributed to a wide range of social and family issues, including marital and child abuse, property crimes, and job absenteeism (Spooner, 2019).

There was evidence of extensive alcohol usage in Zambia. According to the Zambia Demographic Health Survey (2013), 76% of men drank alcohol at that time; 45% had done so in the three months prior to the survey, and 31% had done so at a time more than three months earlier. Only 23% of women admitted to drinking alcohol, with 9% of them doing so in the month prior to the survey and 14% admitting to having done so at a time more than one month earlier. The survey report's authors highlighted that alcohol intake differed by gender and by age. According to the research, alcohol use among females aged 15 to 19 was 5.3%, compared to 22% among males in the same age group. In comparison to their male counterparts, women aged 40 to 49 had a figure of 17% while men had a figure of 57.3%. According to data published in The Global News Wire (2020) there has been an increase in the prevalence of alcohol abuse among young people in Zambia. Children as young as 9 years old could frequently be found in bars or consuming alcohol on the streets.

In a 2001 survey conducted in Lusaka's Kanyama and Chinyika neighbourhoods by the Kanyama Youth Program Trust, it was shown that 61% of adults and 19.4% of youths aged 10 to 21 consumed alcohol. According to the report, 86% of the respondents made comments about how easily available alcohol is. According to the same study, 79% of adults and teenagers consumed alcohol on special events such weddings, wedding receptions, celebrations, and religious ceremonies.

2.2 FACTORS THAT LEAD TO ALCOHOL ABUSE AMONG STUDENTS

Numerous authors and researchers have demonstrated that there are numerous underlying causes of alcohol consumption among college students. According to Rice (2021), both children from wealthy and those from impoverished households experience the effects of alcohol addiction in a university environment. According to Shoemaker (2014), there are a number of environmental, biological, and psychological elements that contribute to alcohol

consumption. NACADA (2004) lists socially and economically unstable households, peer pressure, and psychological states such as the search for identity, fun, curiosity, and a negative self-image (low self-esteem) as contributory factors.

2.2.1 Academic stress

Stress is a well-documented risk factor for alcohol both alcohol use and misuse in undergraduates. A study by Kerr, (2004) reported that self-described stress levels increased in college. The transition period between high school and college is marked by increases in alcohol use and high stress levels, alongside new social circles and increases in school workload. Mainly stress might be related to the Schoolwork and the pressure to perform well, the Pressure from parents and family and also from Living away from home which comes with financial responsibilities including Relationships and Challenges related to mental health disorders, such as anxiety, depression. Previous studies show college student stress and alcohol use/misuse. For example, students who report high levels of stress tend to report more substance. Stress and alcohol also appear to be linked; Park, (2014) tracked college student's daily stress levels and alcohol consumption, showing that on days when students reported more stress, they also reported consuming more alcohol. Typically, if a college student is drinking alcohol to cope with stress, the more time goes on, the more frequently they will drink and in greater quantities. And these patterns of alcohol abuse can have larger implications for an individual's behavioural health.

2.2.2 Student drinking habits/patterns

The amount of alcohol that enters the brain and how impaired a person becomes depend on how many drinks are consumed and how quickly. The amount of liquid in a person's glass, can, or bottle does not always correspond to the amount of alcohol in the beverage. Student drinking patterns vary from normal or standard drinkers to binge drinker and heavy drinkers. A standard

drink is one that contains 14 grams (0.6 fluid ounces) of pure alcohol. 12 ounces of normal beer, which typically has around 5% alcohol, 5 ounces of wine, which typically contains around 12% alcohol, and 1.5 ounces of distilled spirits, which often contain around 40% alcohol, all contain this. Standard-drink definitions vary widely across countries, from 8 grams of alcohol in Iceland and the United Kingdom to 20 grams in Austria (NIAAA, 2017).

NIAAA (2017), defines binge drinking as a pattern of drinking alcohol that brings blood alcohol concentration to 0.08 percent or 0.08 grams of alcohol per decilitre or higher. For a typical adult, this pattern corresponds to consuming 5 or more drinks (male), or 4 or more drinks (female), in about 2 hours. Some college students, however, drink at least twice as much, a practice known as high-intensity drinking. A study conducted in the U S found that nearly 33% of full-time college students between the ages of 18 and 22 who consumed alcohol in the previous month also engaged in binge drinking. 1 In this study, binge drinking was defined as having five or more drinks in a single sitting for men and four or more for women. Numerous research have demonstrated that during their first year of college, students increase their alcohol use. Students build their identities and social networks throughout their first year of college, and drinking alcohol is frequently a component of this process. It is not surprising that first-year students frequently socialize in a drinking setting and make up the biggest percentage of partygoers since being a member of a group, or "fitting in," is a primary driving reason for heavy episodic drinking among university students.

A study conducted in Uganda found that Drinking patterns among university students have been found to be high. In the study, 'Prevalence and associated factors of alcohol use patterns among university students in Uganda', Dr Louis Henry Kamulegeya, a public health specialist at Makerere University's College of Health Sciences, estimated that nearly 15.3% were low-risk drinkers and 17.4% binge drinkers (Machado, 2013). According to various research, heavy drinking among students is related to living away from the parents' house. Students who live

with their parents tend not abuse alcohol than those on their own. Living in student housing, on campuses, or in private residences, whether with roommates or alone, results in less frequent exposure to parental supervision and increased opportunity to participate in harmful behaviours like drinking (Machado, 2013).

2.2.3 Peer Pressure

According to the Oteyo and Kariuki (2019) study conducted in Nakuru public day schools, peer group influence had the biggest impact on high rates of alcohol and tobacco misuse among high school students. Drug addicts, like other individuals, want approval for their actions from their friends, whom they try to persuade to take up their habit in an effort to get acceptability, claims the United Nations (2012), the calibre of the peer group determines whether peer pressure has a positive or negative effect. Unfortunately, the same peer pressure that keeps a group of people acting in accordance with a socially acceptable code of behaviour can also steer a vulnerable person in the wrong direction. According to a study by Kariuki (2018) conducted in Nairobi schools, the majority of drug users had drug-using acquaintances.

According to several studies (Arata, Stafford, & Tims, 2003; D'Amico et.al, 2015; Henry & Kobus, 2007; Pearson & Mitchell, 2020 Oetting, Deffenbacher, & Donnermeyer, 2018), peer relationships are associated with teenage substance use. Teens, especially younger female teens, have been shown to be more vulnerable to peer pressure, which has been connected to teen substance use (Killeya-Jones & Costanzo, 2017). It has been discovered that peer attitudes and actions towards drinking matter more to girls than to boys. According to a Uganda Youth Development Link research, 60% of secondary school students consume alcohol. Peer pressure and the desire to explore were two of the variables identified by the study as being the most prevalent. Other significant concerns included readily available and inexpensive alcohol, poor parental role modelling, and unsuitable school and community environments.

Regarding peer pressure, they claimed that the need to fit in and avoid being viewed negatively by friends was a major motivator for many students. This perspective is in line with Bourne's (2015) claim that young people experience pressure to fit in and partake in activities that their friends are undertaking. As a result, many of the students started abusing drugs, especially when they saw their peers abusing alcohol and narcotics. In support of this conclusion, Kiiru (2014) believes that peer pressure pushes young people to use drugs under the mistaken belief that some drugs boost strength, increase hunger for food, and give wisdom as well as bravery to confront life.

2.2.4 Family background

Another element that contributes to alcohol misuse among students is the interpersonal sphere. According to Coggans and McKellar (2014) this domain is connected to the adolescent's social relationships with friends, family, and near relatives. The interpersonal domain also examines how poorly a family raises its young children as a result of difficult family conditions (Barret & Turner, 2015; Lysnskey et al, 2012). The same domain is also connected to weak parental supervision (Stattin & Kerr, 2020) and low parental discipline (Chassin, 2004). The family structure is included under the interpersonal domain since it affects an individual, for as when they are raised by a single parent or in a divorced couple's household.

The link between drug usage and the home environment has been discussed in great detail. The primary socialising forces for a youngster are their family, especially their parents. According to Muthigani (2015), a child learns their first rules of behaviour from their parents and other nearby adults. She goes on to say that if a youngster notices a discrepancy between their parents' teaching and behaviour, it fosters uncertainty, which persists throughout adolescence and results in aberrant behaviour. According to Shoemaker (2014), poor, inconsistent, or abusive parental punishment is a contributing factor to delinquency, such as the consumption of alcohol

and marijuana. Youth delinquency is consistently correlated with the manner in which parents interact with their children and the overall environment of the family.

Children who come from homes with weak family ties, frequent conflict, physical or sexual abuse, or psychological stress are more likely to try alcohol because these conditions tend to isolate kids from their families and make them turn to alcohol to dull their emotional suffering (NIDA, 2013). There is a chance that a child will use alcohol if their family does not provide them with adequate emotional or physical care, support, or guidance, or if they are subjected to mental, physical, or sexual abuse (UNODC, 2014). According to a Victorian government survey from 2009, children who have experienced sexual abuse are more prone to drink alcohol.

The likelihood that a student will try alcohol increases if they come from a home with weak family ties, frequent conflict, physical or sexual abuse, or psychological stress because these conditions tend to isolate kids from their families and lead them to turn to alcohol to dull their emotional pain (NIDA, 2013). There is a chance that a child will use alcohol if their family does not provide them with adequate emotional or physical care, support, or guidance, or if they are subjected to mental, physical, or sexual abuse (UNODC, 2014). According to a Victorian government survey from 2019, children who have experienced sexual abuse are more prone to drink alcohol.

2.2.5 Personal Factors

The majority of students cite alcohol's pleasing taste and the ability to make people feel good or euphoric as its primary appeals as justifications for drinking. Peer pressure and other conformity-related factors are also discussed. In fact, peers are frequently the ones who introduce adolescents to alcohol for the first time, and alcohol usage may be the result of peer pressure to fit in with the group. Teenagers also mention enhancement-related motivations

(NIAAA, 2014). Along with a high amount of social engagement, adolescence is also characterised by strong sensation and novelty seeking, impulsivity, and risk-taking behaviours. Enhancement goals can include the desire to try new things, get high, or engage in exciting but potentially risky activities. Coping motives are a different set of causes for drinking (Campbell et al., 2019). Students drink to deal with their challenging situations and anticipate that it would help them unwind, release stress, and forget about their issues. Teenagers with troubled families, internalising behaviours, unhappiness, upset, feeling unwell, lacking in confidence, and those who have experienced bullying or other mistreatment are more likely to give these explanations. Due to all of these factors, adolescents are more susceptible to developing an alcohol use disorder (Kuntsche et al., 2017).

2.2.6 Environmental Factors

External environmental elements in the community could have an impact on drinking. These elements, according to Newman et al (2011), include the prevalence of drinking establishments near schools and the availability of reasonably priced alcohol. According to Chaloupka and Wechsler (2016), more people will drink if alcohol is less expensive. Drink specials, kegs, and other inexpensive alcohol supplies promote excessive drinking and intoxication. Alcohol advertising encourages increasing alcohol intake by contributing to the development of a culture that believes excessive alcohol consumption and use are commonplace activities.

When legal substances like cigarettes and alcohol are also readily available, such as heroin, cocaine, and mandrax, drug use may result, according to Kaguthi, the NACADA director in 2014. This encourages young people to consume and eventually abuse drugs. The survey claims that the most significant factor contributing to the prevalence of substance use and abuse is the easy access to most drugs. The accessibility of drugs and alcohol in the community, according to Public Safety Canada (2009), encouraged young people to abuse them.

2.2.6 Availability of Access Financial Resources

This encourages teaching proper use of available financial resources as well as putting only necessary resources in the hands of the teens, and in doing so, fights against age of onset of drugs and substance use are delayed as well as eliminated for an entire generation. Nguyen (2011) established that when financial resources availability is considered, it proved to be more influential of teens engaging in substance use than having parents with higher education and good jobs. Teenagers that practise good ethics will be able to delay the age at which they start using drugs and alcohol as well as trying them, leading to a society free of drugs and alcohol since continuity and rate of spread will reduce.

2.3 EFFECTS OF ALCOHOL ABUSE

The immediate physical effects of alcohol consumption, according to Web Med (2009), can range from minor mood changes to total loss of coordination, vision (drowsiness), balance, poor judgement, and speech. After a person stops drinking, the aforementioned bodily consequences, which might be signs of acute alcohol intoxication or drunkenness, often subside within a few hours. A 0.08 percent alcohol concentration in the blood is considered proof of intoxication by many law enforcement organisations around the world, including those in South Africa (Youth Risk Behaviour Survey, 2009). According to Getchell, Pippin, and Varnes (2015), higher blood alcohol levels can damage the liver, impede brain function, and eventually lead to unconsciousness. The same authors also noted that alcohol poisoning, which can be lethal, can result from a severe overdose. They continued by describing chronic alcoholism as a lethal disease that progresses over time and is characterised by an unceasing desire for alcohol along with a physical dependence on it and a lack of control. Others may or may not be aware of the physical dependence on alcohol. While some chronic alcoholics became extremely intoxicated, others maintained enough control to appear to manage daily affairs in a close to normal manner. The Web by Dent, Grube, and Biglan (2018) emphasised the possibility that alcohol misuse, if it became alcoholism, might result in a variety of physical illnesses, such as hypoglycaemia, hypertension, brain and heart damage, and hypoglycaemia.

The DSM IV in Barlow and Durand (2017), gave a list of alcohol related induced disorders as persistent dementia, psychotic disorders with hallucinations, psychotic disorders with delusions, mood disorders, sleep disorders and sexual dysfunction.

According to revelations made by a Kabwe High School student during the first African Youth Day celebrations, youths who abuse alcohol end up getting involved in vices like prostitution and early pregnancies, HIV/AIDS, foul language, and involvement in the use of strong drugs. This information was published in Zambia's Post Newspaper on November 3, 2009. The newspaper article continued to focus on the negative effects of teen alcohol addiction, including school abandonment, poor health, and time spent in jail for criminal activity, and ultimately early mortality.

Population-based data supported the association between alcohol use and sexual behaviour (Lugalla et al., 2016). Amayo (2016) and Ao et al. (2016) both noted that alcohol usage was particularly harmful among populations that were more likely to contract HIV, such as mobile populations, commercial sex workers, and young people. The transmission issue, however, had previously been disregarded or only superficially addressed by HIV prevention efforts (Morris et al., 2016). Health professionals working on HIV/AIDS programmes began to take an interest in highlighting and addressing the role that alcohol abuse played in promoting risky sexual behaviour, accelerating the progression of disease, decreasing the efficacy of HIV treatment, and decreasing adherence to medication schedules as the situation started to change.

2.4 MEASURES TO MITIGATE ALCOHOL ABUSE

According to Phillips (2014), there are a variety of intervention techniques that can be used, including educating, confronting a drug addict about their actions, demonstrating love, supporting the addict's family and friends, and chemical dependency therapy and detoxification. The metrics can be used on a variety of scales, including the individual, the family, the school, the community, the country, and the world.

Studies show a significant connection between young people's alcohol and drug usage and the erosion of family values (Gitahi and Mwangi, 2007). Alcohol consumption was limited in traditional societies to older age groups and special occasions. Even then, drinking was frowned upon and alcohol use was strictly regulated. Alcohol abuse by youngsters as young as 10 years old poses a threat to not only their own safety and the safety of their families, but also to the health of the entire country (Daily Nation, 2017). Families and society as a whole have a responsibility to make sure that children develop in a setting that encourages moral principles and a more structured way of life. Lack of a proper value system in the society is likely to lead to drug abuse, which in turn would ruin the family life even further. Hence the family has a major role to play in mitigating alcohol abuse among school boys and girls. The family need to be more involved in the lives of these boys and girls and need to work hand in hand with the school.

Another strategy for reducing alcohol misuse in schoolboys and girls is peer-to-peer counselling. Peer education projects have been implemented by institutions in an effort to reduce risky sexual behaviour, unintended pregnancies, STIs, including HIV/AIDS, and drug misuse by enhancing the quality of counselling and service delivery to students. The project's peer outreach campaign, which teaches students to encourage responsible behaviour among their peers, is its key component. Showing films, having follow-up conversations, offering counselling at people's homes, and giving public lectures are some of the actions involved in peer counselling. According to Tobler et al. (2019), students will be less likely to abuse drugs and alcohol if there is better communication between professors, students, and peers. Although such activities can go a long way in addressing and curbing drug-related problems, they are secondary to the role of the family in socializing children and the youth in the right direction. The family is the basic building block of every culture.

CHAPTER 3

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology that will be followed in this investigation is outlined in this section. The study type, variables, study locations, and study population are all discussed, as well as the sampling method and sample size, data collecting plan, data collection technique and tools, data collection and quality control, data processing and analysis, ethical consideration, and pre-testing.

3.1 STUDY AREA

Kitwe district is one of the big cities located in Copperbelt Province and is a host to a various number of tertiary institutions.

My area of study was the Copperbelt University. This is because it is one of the biggest institutions in the district.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN

This study will employ a cross-sectional study. In this study, both qualitative and quantitative methods of capturing data were used so as to enable the researcher to obtain findings in a more detailed way. The qualitative method was be used in order to get in depth information from the study participants by asking more questions via

the questionnaire while the qualitative method was used for the numerical analysis of data.

3.3 STUDY POPULATION

The study population was all third year students in the second semester, both male and female, who are currently enrolled at The Copperbelt University Riverside Campus.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION

The study population was 1130 students. To determine sample size, Slovin's formula (Slovin, 1960) was applied:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where N is the population size and e is the margin of error.

$$n = 1130 / (1 + 1130(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 295 \text{ participants}$$

3.5 SAMPLING PROCEDURE

This study was used Simple random sampling to select the study participants as this will help avoid biases by allowing for all students to have a chance of being selected so a representative inference of the population can be found. This was achieved by randomly selecting a subject from the population. Each student will only have one chance to be selected in the sample i.e., a random sample cannot be sampled again (sampling without replacement).

3.5.1 Inclusion Criteria

All third year students in the second semester who are registered for the current academic year.
Students who consent to participate in the study.

3.5.2 Exclusion Criteria

Third year second semester Students who are not registered for the current academic year.
Students who do not consent to participate in the study.

3.6 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Data was collected using a structured self-administered questionnaire prepared in English. The questionnaire were divided into three sections. These sections include information on social, economic and service related factors contributing to alcohol abuse.

3.7 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

After checking raw data for completeness and accuracy, data gathered from the respondents was exported to SSPSS for analysis. In preparation for analysis, the exported data was cleaned, verified, and coded. Frequencies and percentages were used to portray categorical variables in tables and charts.

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical approval to carry out this research was sought from the Tropical Diseases Research Centre (TDRC) Research Ethics Committee in Ndola. Permission to undertake the study at The Copperbelt University was obtained from The Copperbelt University management. Individuals who participated in this study were provided with informed consent forms and they will remain anonymous as their information will be kept private and confidential.

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Demographics

A total of 295 questionnaires were administered to students at the COPPERBELT University.

Despite this, 253 of the returned questionnaires had complete answers.

4.1.1 Sex of respondents:

Figure 2 Gender distribution

The figure 2, above represents the gender of the respondents. According to the data, 131(52%) were males and 122(48%) were female. the respondents with the highest frequency were the men.

4.1.2 Age of respondents

Figure 3 age of respondents

The age groups of the respondents are depicted in Figure 5.2. The data reveals that 52(7.11%) were between the ages of 18 and 21, 109 (43.08%) were between the ages of 22 and 25, 73 (28.85%) were between the ages of 26-29 and 18(7.11%) were over the age of 30. The highest frequency was seen in the 22-25 year old age group.

	Yes/ (%)	No/ (%)
Family members/parents who drink	174 (68.77%)	79 (31.23%)
Lack of parental involvement	162 (64.03%)	91 (35%)
Unstable families	136 (53.75%)	117 (46.25%)
Harsh parents	96 (37.94%)	157 (62.06%)
Parents okay with children drinking	151 (59.92%)	102 (40.48%)

4.2 Social factors leading to alcohol abuse

4.2.1 Family factors

The table 1 shows the social factors that are contributing to alcohol abuse. The table shows that 174(%) said yes to having parents/family members who drink, 166(%) said yes to lack of parental involvement, 136(%) said yes to unstable families, 96(%) said yes to having harsh parents and 118(%) said yes to having parents that are okay with children drinking. The respondents who agreed had the highest frequency which shows that family factors contribute to students drinking.

4.2.2 Personal factors

Figure 4 above shows personal factors that influence students drinking. Peer pressure had 205(81.03%) students agreeing, 158(58.5%) said yes to curiosity contributing to abuse, 115(45.45%) agreed with low self-esteem, 153(60.74%) said yes to history of Abuse and 133(52.57%) said yes to having friends who drink.

4.2.3 Academic Stress and alcohol abuse:

The figure 8 above shows the relationship between academic Stress among students and alcohol abuse. The response shows that 139(55.17%) said yes and 114(44.83%) said no. The respondents who agreed had a high frequency of therefore showing that academic Stress does contribute to student drinking.

4.3 Economic factors leading to alcohol abuse

4.3.1 Parental economic status

Figure 5 shows the replies to the question of whether parental socioeconomic position influences college students' alcohol abuse. The figure shows that 172(68.25%) agreed. The respondents who said yes had the highest frequency, therefore showing that parental economic status contributes to abuse.

4.3.2 Concentration of drinking outlets

Figure 6 shows the response to concentration of drinking outlets contribute to alcohol abuse among students. The response rates were as follows: 197(78.17%) said yes and 56(21.83) said no. The majority of the respondents said yes therefore showing that there is a concentration of drinking outlets.

4.3.3 Availability of cheap alcohol

Figure 7 shows the availability of cheap alcohol at CBU. From the 253 respondents, 147(%) said yes to the availability of cheap alcohol while 106(%) said no. This shows that there is availability of drinking outlets at the university.

4.4 Service related factors and alcohol abuse

4.4.1 University policy on alcohol abuse.

Item	Yes	%
Bought Possessed and consumed	231	91.3
May Not be Bought Possessed and Consumed	22	8.7
Total	253	100

The table 2 above shows that the university policy on alcohol drinking. 231(91.3%) said yes to alcohol being bought, possessed and consumed at the university and 22(8.78%) said may not be bought, possessed and consumed.

4.4.2 Measures put in place to reduce abuse among students:

	Yes (%)	No (%)
Guidance and counselling	187(74.21%)	66(26%)
Seminars on alcohol abuse	110(43.65%)	143(56.75%)
Peer talks	96(38.1%)	157(62.3%)

Formation of anti-alcohol clubs	76(30.16%)	177(70.24%)
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The tables above shows the measures that have been put in place in order to reduce alcohol abuse. The findings show guidance and counselling 187(74%), seminars 110(43.65%), peer talks 96(38%) and anti-alcohol clubs 76(30%)

4.4.3 Effectiveness of measures

item	Yes	no	total
Effectiveness of measures	62(24%)	190(75%)	253(100%)

The table above shows the effectiveness of the measures put in place. The results show that the respondents who said yes were 62(24%) and 190(75%).

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter addresses the study's results in light of its objectives. This discussion also makes an effort to respond to the research questions by summarizing the key findings and, where appropriate, contrasting them with earlier findings in the examined literature.

5.1 Social factors that are contributing to alcohol abuse

Social influences on alcohol use are a collection of societal forces that can lead to alcoholism.

These could include one's family, deviant peer affiliation, and school influence.

(Gruenewald,2015)

Family factors such as family members/parents who drink, unstable families, parents who are okay with children drinking were looked at. The finding indicated that family members who drink (68.77%), lack of parental involvement 162(64.03%), unstable families 136(53.75) and having parents who are okay with children drinking 151(59%) all said yes. This shows that family factors do indeed contribute to students drinking A study conducted by Wieczorek(2015) showed links between alcohol use and parental drinking, having unstable families and family dynamics. Children are more likely to use alcohol if both parents consume alcohol, and higher parental alcohol consumption is linked to alcohol use, therefore agreeing with the study.

The results are consistent with Walton and Roberts' (2014) analysis of the behavioral, emotional, and cognitive styles of an individual's personal profile as well as personality traits like hostility, low self-esteem, and difficulty in exercising self-control lead to alcohol use. According to the study, peer pressure and having history of alcohol use is one of the main factors that contribute to students drinking. The findings are also in agreement with the findings from the study by Oteyo and Kariuki (2018) that pointed out that peer group influence had the greatest influence among students.

The study found that academic Stress 139(55.17%) did in fact contribute to students drinking. According to a research done by Busary (2012), The greatest sources of academic stress, according to students, are studying for and writing exams, assignments competing with classmates for the highest grade, and the overwhelming amount of material to master in a short amount of time. In coping with these stressors, students resort to alcohol drinking. (Busari, 2012).

5.2 Economic factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students

The study aimed to determine the parental economic status effect on alcohol abuse among students. The findings were that 172(68.98%) agreed with parental economic status contributes to students drinking. This is in line with a study conducted by Hjern (2013) found that People who come from wealthier families are much more likely to be heavy drinkers and to acquire alcohol use disorders.

The study also sought to identify concentration of drinking outlets and availability of cheap alcohol. The findings were that 197(78.17%) agreed with the institution having concentration of drinking outlets and 147(58%) agreed with availability of cheap alcohol. A study conducted by Andersen (2016) showed that People's decision to consume alcohol is influenced by the presence of alcoholic beverages in surrounding places. In fact, when there are more bars and clubs with alcohol close to the school, there are higher instances of drinking among college

students. Last but not least, alcohol advertising frequently portrays Alcohol use and overuse as acceptable and desirable, supporting favorable views toward drinking. The results of this study were consistent with those of earlier studies that asserted that economic factors, such as inexpensive alcohol and easy access to bars increased the likelihood of drinking. (Swahn, 2011)

5.3 Service related factors contributing to alcohol abuse among university students

The study compared the university policy on alcohol drinking and mitigation measures put in place to alcohol abuse. 91.67% did agree that the university policy allows students to buy, possess and consume alcohol.

Mitigation measures put in place at the university showed that guidance and counselling services 187(74.21%), seminars 110 (43.65%), peer talks 96(38.1%) and anti-alcohol clubs 76(30.16%). The results showed that the measures put in place are not effective with (75%) responding with no to effectiveness of the measures.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

The main objective of the study was to investigate the factors leading to alcohol abuse at the COPPERBELT University Riverside Campus. The study revealed that Parents who drink and parents who don't involve themselves in their children's lives are the main family factors that contribute to alcohol abuse among students. Based on the results, it can be stated that lack of self-control, curiosity and peer pressure are the main personal variables that lead to alcohol consumption among students. The study also reviewed that economic factors such as parental Economic status, and availability of drinking outlets and cheap alcohol also contributes to abuse. The lack of proper mitigation measures on student's that are abusing alcohol abuse increases the prevalence of abuse among the students. Therefore, proper mitigation measures are needed to curb abuse among students.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. A supportive campus atmosphere that promotes active co-curricular activities including sports, music, drama, clubs, societies, movies, and football viewing is necessary to eradicate alcoholism among students. These kinds of activities will help students feel like they belong and have a purpose in life, which will lessen their boredom and laziness, two things that are positively linked to student alcoholism.
2. The government must continue to demonstrate its leadership and commitment by assisting with the execution of alcohol-related policies by providing the necessary training and dedicating the human and financial resources to do so.

3. One strategy to deal with this issue is to encourage parents and guardians to be mindful of their alcohol consumption when around their dependents and children. As demonstrated by this study and numerous others, parents and caregivers play a significant role in shaping a child's personality and behavior.

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APPENDICES

QUESTIONNAIRE

Please mark your answers with “X”

Part 1, respondent’s profile:

1. What is your sex?

- a. Female
- b. Male

2. How old are you?

- a. 18-21
- b. 22-25
- c. 26-29
- d. Above 30

3. What is your Marital Status?

- a. Single
- b. Married
- C. Divorced
- d. Widowed

4. What is your religious affiliation?

- a. Christian []
- b. Islam []
- c. Hinduism []
- d. None []
- e. Others (specify) []

Part 2, Social factors:

A. Which of the following family factors contribute to alcohol abuse?

	Item	Yes	No
1	Having parents and family members that drink		
2	Lack of parental involvement		
3	Unstable families		
4	Having parents that are harsh disciplinarians		
5	Having parents that are not strict		
6	Having parents that are okay with children drinking		

B. Which of the following personal factors contribute to university boys and girls to abuse alcohol?

	Item	Yes	No
1	Curiosity		
2	Peer pressure		
3	Low self-esteem		
4	History of Abuse		

5	Having friends that drink		
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Part3, Economic related factors:

A. Which of the following Economic factors contributing to alcohol abuse:

	Item	Yes	No
1	Do you think parental social-economic status contributes to student alcohol abuse?		
2	Do you think most students tend to direct funds towards the purchase of alcohol every now and then due to different social economic classes/statuses?		
3	Is there a concentration of drinking outlets at school or near school?		
4	Is there availability of cheap alcohol?		

Part 4: service related factors:

1. Do you think academic stress such as assignments, tests/ quizzes and exams contributes to students drinking?

a. Yes []

b. No []

2. What is the university policy on alcohol drinking?

a. May be bought, possessed, and consumed. []

b. May not be bought, possessed, and consumed. []

3. What has been put in place to reduce alcohol abuse among students?

		Yes	No
a	Guidance and counselling services		
b	Seminars about the dangers of alcohol abuse		
c	Peer talks		
d	Formation of anti-alcohol clubs		
e	Nothing has been put in place		

4. Would you say that the measures that have been put in place have been effective in reducing alcohol abuse among students?

a. Yes []

b. No []

APPENDIX IV: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET AND CONSENT FORM

Introduction

Hello, my name is Terence Ngobola from Rusangu University and I am carrying out research on “The factors that lead too alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University in Kitwe District”.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study will be to obtain information that will be used to determine the factors that lead to an increase in alcohol abuse among students at The Copperbelt University, riverside campus.

Study Procedures

The study will involve answering questions provided in the self-administered questionnaire. You will be required to answer these questions only once. No any sort of medical examination will be carried out on you.

Confidentiality

The answers to the questions will be kept confidential and a unique identifier only known to the researcher will be used instead of your name. Personal information about you will not be released to anyone and will not be used in any publications from this study.

Study Benefits

There are no direct benefits to you for participating in this study. However, the information obtained from this study may inform the development, implementation, and enforcement of alcohol related policies and interventions at different society levels in Zambia. This should help reduce the number of people not only abusing alcohol but also suffering health conditions likely to be occasioned by alcohol consumption.

Study Risks

There are no health risks associated with participating in this study. However, you may just have to spare some few minutes from your normal schedule to respond to the questions in the questionnaire.